

Influence of Western Music on Rabindra Sangeet in context with Global Music – A Study

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Abstract

This study will present a comprehensive look at different modes of Rabindra Sangeet and Western music in context with Global Music. The purpose is to traverse the influence of western music on Rabindra Sangeet through the spiritual significance of Rabindra Sangeet by Guru Rabindranath Tagore. The objective of the research is to explore different songs of Rabindra Sangeet having western influence at different levels. 'Valmiki Pratibha', 'Kalamrigaya' and different parjaay's songs come to mind when mentioning Rabindra Sangeet composed under the influence of foreign music. Different aspects of Rabindra sangeet will be enlightened by the researcher and the vision of Rabindranath Tagore that how western music is been utilized in Rabindra Sangeet will be explored. The researcher will follow the method and steps for this research article on Rabindra Sangeet and the process of research work will include Interviews, review of people, gathering materials, field work when required, CD, DVD, books, Recordings, Documentary etc. The music of Europe is strangely connected with the real life of the people. This music has expressed the diversity of human life by translating it into music. There is no subject that Europe has not composed songs about. Europe is far ahead in diversity. Our music lacked human diversity. As European civilization changed our frame of mind, we did not want to be confined to a single permanent image. As a result, we got National Anthem, inspirational songs, war songs, laughter songs, death songs, wedding songs, various festival songs etc. through Rabindra Sangeet. Tagore's songs are superlative in the country in such variety of subjects.

Keywords: Rabindra Sangeet, Western Music, Valmiki Pratibha, Kalamrigaya, Different parjaays in Rabindra Sangeet.

Research Paper

Introduction

Since ancient times in India, the practice of reciting poetry in harmony has been prevalent. The Ramayana and Mahabharata are still performed in tune. Eventoday Hindu and Urdu poetry is performed under the shelter of melody. In ancient Europe too, Homer's epics was recited to the harp. Folktales of our country and ballads of Europe used to entertain the audience as poetic songs. The earliest works of Bengali literature are Jayadev's Geeta Govinda or Baru Chandidas's Shri Krishna Kirtans as songs or dramas. Charyapads, the oldest examples of bengali poetry are known as Charyageet in literary circles. Even at the beginning of British rule in the country, Panchali songs composed in Bengali

language were popular. In fact, in our country, the correlation between poetry and music is easily seen. "The expression of folk music is multifaceted. The expression of folk music in native vernacular languages, the pronunciation of the language and the logical phonetic outline of the melody must be clear. Fragments of people's life, isolation, feelings etc. have become one like the dust of the road and have awakened in the spirit of folk music." (Kuthial 4)

During Rabindranath Tagore's travel in Europ, he became acquainted with the doctrines of the western composer Hagnar and the philosopher Spencer, and based on their ideals, he composed music in Valmiki Pratibha and Kalamrigaya. It was as a result of this attempt to add music to poetry that he composed his ballads.

“Western musicologists consider the phenomenal development of harmony to be the greatest development of music. Melody is considered by combining many things and folk music. So, for foreign music, our Raag music and folk music even primitive music belongs to the ethnomusicology research.” (Roy 3)

Tagore was both poet and composer. “Gurudev won the Nobel Prize in 1913 when his book Geetanjali was published in 1910.” (Ray 85)

Most of his short poems are acceptable as songs. He had added melody in almost all the poems. A few poetry books also have clear references to songs, such as Geetali, Gitimala, Gitanjali etc. Even though melody is the soul of a song, its structure has to be formed by words. It is performed as a song by adding melody to the lyrical part. Tagore gained special skill in composing these kind of music.

Composition of Western Notes

Like the number of swaras in Indian music, the number of shudh swara in western music is seven. The names of these seven tones are Do, Re, Me, Fa, So, La, Si, these tones are abbreviated as C, D, E, F, G, A, B.

A comparison of western music with Indian music shows such a relationship - Sa = C, R = D, Ga = E, Ma = F, Pa = G, Dha = A, Ni = B. The notes in the sequence are also called First, Second, Third, Fourth, Fifth, Sixth and Seventh notes. These tones are also called by the other names. For Example -

“The first note C is called - Tonic

Second Tone D is called - Supertonic

Third note E is called - Mediant

The fourth tone F is called - Subdominant

The fifth note G is called - Dominant

The sixth note A is called - Submediant or Super dominant

The seventh note B is called - Subtonic” (Roy 86)

As in Indian music, there are two types of distorted tones in the western music, that is Sharp and Flat tone. Shudh Swar in western music is called Natural note. A feature of western music is the use of different names for sounds when pronounced than when written.

As in Indian music, seven shudh Swar notes are called saptak, in western music, eight notes are taken to form octave. Any note twice as high as a note called an octave. As in Indian music - Sa, Re, Ga, Ma, Pa, Dha, Ni, Sa as in Western Music C D E F G A B C.

Tagore and Western Music

Gurudev was exposed to western music at an early age, through the music of his grandfather Jyotirindranath. The wave of foreign music was also felt in the Tagore family. Interest in gaining knowledge and education in western music was shown and organ was introduced in the house worship music. Jyotirindranath inspired Rabindranath by playing the piano. Jyotirindranath used to play various foreign tunes on the piano and Rabindranath Tagore used to recite them. “It is said that Rabindranath Tagore’s grandfather Prince Dwarkanath studied western music with a German musician. His son Devendranath also learned piano from a foreign teacher.” (Kajal 60)

“It was Jyotirindranath Tagore who experimented with composition of English and Bengali songs by mixing different ragas. Living in such an environment Rabindranath Tagore was also influenced by western music.” (Koser 21) After this, the poet travelled to foreign countries in his youth, he was directly introduced to western music. No door was closed to Rabindranath in the environment in which he grew up as a child. In order to increase his musical wealth, the poet has taken many things from Indian and Desi music on the one hand, as well as extracted many things from western music. “In Rabindra Kavya, God, man, nature are all different forms of an infinite blissful pot. sometimes the sense of God has merged into the intimate spiritual bond of human love, the finite sands of nature have grasped the hand of the infinite. The entire rasa is united in the bond of sympathy of this free soul. The poet tried to divide this spectrum into several stages in the parjaay. These categories are Pooja Parjaay, Swadesh Parjaay, Prem Parjaay, Prakriti Parjaay, Bichitro Parjaay, Aanushthanik Parjaay.” (Dutta 207)

In the way shown by Jyotirindranath, Rabindranath did not follow the path of limitation but tried to create something new by combining desi and foreign songs. Hence we have got many new types of songs in the repertoire of Indian music which no lyricist has thought before.

Influence of Western music on Rabindra Sangeet

Rabindranath Tagore adopted a lot of Indian and Desi music in order to increase his musical wealth, he did not neglect western music either, that is, he was liberal about music. He explored and accepted the Global music. He became familiar with Global musical thought by reading the writings of Hart Spencer. Tagore’s inimitable quote about European and Indian music -

“Its true that there is a fundamental difference in our music with Europe. Harmony is the main object of European music and Raga-Ragini is our mainstay. Europe is focused on diversity; we are on one.” (Gosh 23)

Indira Devi talks about the influence of western music on Tagore in book Triveni sangam of Rabindra Sangeet- “It is no exaggeration to say that almost all the songs which the poet himself has heard or which others have brought him from abroad have offered him at the altar of worship.” (Gosh 23)

In fact, Tagore experimented tirelessly for musical excellence throughout his life and as a result we have Rabindra music influenced by foreign tones. Below is the short list of Rabindra Sangeet with western originals:

Sr. No	Rabindra Sangeet	Parjaay	Raga	Taal	Original western song
1.	“Kali kali bolo re	Balmiki Pratibha	-	Dadra	Nancy Lee
2.	Tui aai re	Natya Geeti	Kafi	Jhaptaal	The British Grenadiers
3.	Phule phule dhole dhole	Kaal Mrigaya	-	Khemta	Ye banks and braes of Bonnie Doon
4.	Shokoli phuralo	Kaal Mrigaya	-	Ektaal	Robin Adair
5.	Aha aji e bosonte	Mayar Khela	-	Tritaal	Go where glory waits thee
6.	Mana na manili	Kaal Mrigaya	-	Tritaal	Go where glory waits thee
7.	Ohe doyamoy, nikhil aashray	Porishista	Mishra Bilawal	Kaharwa	Go where glory waits thee
8.	Mori o kahar bacha	Balmiki Pratibha	-	Tritaal	Go where glory waits thee
9.	Kotobaar bhebechinu	Prem O prokriti	-	Ektaal	Drink to me only
10.	O dekhbi re bhai aai re chute	Kaal Mrigaya	-	Khemta	The vicar of Bray
11.	Giyechi she din	Prem O Prokriti	Bhairavi	Jhaptaal	Loves young dream
12.	Purano shei diner kotha	Perm O Prokriti	-	Ektaal	Auld Lang Syne”

Above shortlisted western influenced Rabindra Sangeet information is taken from the book “Proshnottare Rabindra Sangeet by Shambhunath Ghosh. (Ghosh 23-24)

Tagore once said “The purpose of music is to express feelings. Just as rhythm alone, pleasant to the ear, is still unnecessary. Rhythm with feelings is the talk of poets and thinkers, just like only harmony is a body without life - the structure of the body may be beautiful, but it has no life. Singers who call music They place it above the music, they place it on some inanimate in animate melody, I place it on the living immortal. They want the melody above the lyrics, I want the lyrics above the melody. They sit down. To set the tone, I set the tone to set the tone.” (Gosh 29)

Outside the above list, many songs have more or less western influences. Valmiki Pratibha, Kalamrigaya, Mayar Khela etc. show western influence in several songs of each Geetinatya.

Conclusion

Rabindranath Tagore believes that, Indian music is un defined, indescribable melancholy of a solitary nature. The nature and feelings the raga-ragini contains is not unique to any individual. It is infinite, universal. It is the external object of all our worldly happiness and sorrow. it is the song of one and that one is universal. Therefore, our classical music is not for individuals but for entire universe. Its peace, solemnity destroy all worldly narrowness and tension and bring forth a quest for another ethereal realm.

On the other hand, western music is inextricably linked with real life of people. This music expresses all the mundane idiosyncrasies of human life in the form of music. This music is strong and powerful. western music is composed based on all subjects. Because of this, western music is rich in subject diversity. That is why our mind changed under the influence of western music. Tagore also tried to express the joys and sorrows of daily life through music. As a result, National Songs,

war songs, motivational songs, laughter songs, birthday songs, farming songs, harvest songs etc. started to composed in Rabindra Sangeet. This is the special influence of western songs on Rabindra Sangeet.

Indian music ragas and its various taal are vary valuable resources in terms of expression of different types of rasas and expressions and Rabindranath Tagore was advancing by taking shelter of them. But in western music, the notes are arranged in different ways and in different rhythms to express the feelings. Tagore has taken the tunes of different regions of India, he has enriched the repertoire of Rabindra Sangeet as well as Indian music by taking all the tunes of western music which he liked in his composed songs. Thus the influence of western music can be especially felt in Rabindra Sangeet.

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